

A Human Wearable Framework for Physical Human-Robot Interaction

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Abstract—Physical interaction between humans and robots is more and more frequently required in the modern society. We introduce a novel framework endowing robots with the ability to perceive humans while collaborating at the same task. The framework embodies a human wearable system (i.e., motion tracking suit, force/torque sensors shoes) and a probabilistic algorithm for the human floating-base whole-body kinematics and dynamics estimation.

Index Terms—floating-base human dynamics, real-time human joint torque estimation, human wearable system

I. INTRODUCTION

Today’s humans need to collaborate with robots more and more frequently. Robotics community is currently engaged in the development of robotic devices that are able to cooperate via physical contacts with humans in several occupational fields, e.g., in assembly-line factories, in medical rehabilitation for patients or in domestic assistance for elderly people.

Although today’s robots are equipped with all sorts of sophisticated sensors, the onboard technologies do not guarantee the task success when the collaborative task with a human demands a physical contact. If the task is not previously scheduled in the robot control loop, the quality of the interaction decreases because of the unpredictability of the human movements [1]. The robots have to perceive the human partners to mimic the implicit mutual awareness of two collaborative humans [2] [3]. The perception for a robot is equivalent *i*) to *know* the position of the human, *ii*) to *detect* the motion of the human, *iii*) to *quantify* the exchanged contact forces and the human joint torques for the task ergonomics control [4].

We introduce a novel framework endowing robots with the ability to perceive humans while fulfilling a common cooperative task. The framework encompasses a wearable distributed sensor system provided by Xsens [5] with 17 whole-body distributed inertial measurement units (IMUs), and a pair of portable sensorized shoes developed at Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia with four 6-axis force/torque sensors to detect the external forces exchanged by the human with the ground, Fig. 1. Sensor readings are exploited by a probabilistic algorithm for the online whole-body human quantities estimation. The robot controllers can embody the human estimated quantities and adjust the interaction strategy.

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Fig. 1: Human wearable sensorized system.

II. SIMULTANEOUS KINEMATICS AND DYNAMICS HUMAN ESTIMATION

The research objective is to compute the simultaneous floating-base estimation of the human whole-body kinematics and dynamics (i.e., joint torques, internal forces exchanged across joints, external forces acting on links).

A. Modeling

The human is modeled as a floating-base dynamic system of rigid links connected by joints,

$$M(q)\dot{\nu} + C(q, \nu)\nu + G(q) = B\tau + J^T(q) f^x, \quad (1a)$$

$$J(q)\dot{\nu} + \dot{J}(q)\nu = 0, \quad (1b)$$

where M and C are the mass and Coriolis effect matrix, respectively. G is a term accounting for the gravity effect. B is a selector matrix for the joint torques τ . J is the Jacobian operator that maps the system velocity with the velocity of the link where is acting the external force f^x . The system configuration is represented by $q = (q_b, s)$, being q_b the pose of the base with respect to (w.r.t) a generic inertial frame \mathcal{I} and s the joint position vector capturing the topology of the system. Terms $\dot{\nu}$ and ν are the acceleration and velocity of the system, respectively. In particular, $\nu = (v_b, \dot{s})$ where v_b is the base velocity expressed w.r.t. \mathcal{I} and \dot{s} is the joint velocities vector. Contact constraints are captured in Equation (1b).

B. Kinematics estimation

Per each pair of links, the joint position s is computed by solving a link-pairwise inverse kinematics problem via Iopt optimization [6]. The problem is formulated to minimize

the distance between the measured and the computed relative rotations between the frames attached to the link pair. The joint velocity \dot{s} is again computed by the Ipopt solver exploiting the measured link velocity. Pose and velocity of the base w.r.t. the inertial frame are also measured by sensors.

C. Dynamics estimation problem

To solve the dynamic estimation problem, the overall system in (1) is rearranged to an equivalent compact matrix form [7]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y}(s) \\ \mathbf{D}(s) \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{d} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_Y(s, \dot{s}) \\ \mathbf{b}_D(s, \dot{s}) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{Y} is a matrix taking into account the measurements of the sensors, \mathbf{D} is a matrix for the system constraints. Bias terms \mathbf{b}_Y and \mathbf{b}_D are related to the above-listed matrices, respectively. The vector \mathbf{d} embodies kinematics and dynamics quantities of the model. The vector \mathbf{y} contains values measured via sensors, i.e., IMUs accelerations and external forces,

$$\mathbf{y} = [\mathbf{a}_{\text{IMUs}} \quad \mathbf{f}^x]^\top. \quad (3)$$

The solution of the problem is provided by solving the system in (2) for the vector \mathbf{d} via a *Maximum-A-Posteriori* estimator. The estimator maximizes the probability of \mathbf{d} given the measurements reliability. The estimator, therefore, looks for the mean of a conditional probability, i.e., $\mathbf{d} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_{d|y}$ in the Gaussian domain, and its covariance $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{d|y}$,

$$[\boldsymbol{\mu}_{d|y}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{d|y}] = \arg \max_{\mathbf{d}} p(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{y}). \quad (4)$$

III. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The software architecture has been designed for the real-time *i)* acquisition of human data and *ii)* estimation of the whole-body kinematics and dynamics. It is a C++ based architecture consisting of collection of devices and computational units that expose data through custom-made interfaces, Fig. 2. Each sensor has been conceived as a device that runs independently at the sensor frequency. Input data are conveyed through the network and then remapped into the algorithm that computes the kinematics and dynamics estimation. Each unit has been designed to stream the output through the YARP middleware [8] and to visualize each unit output on ROS RViz [9] in real-time.

The framework has been tested during a human gait analysis on a treadmill. The real-time visualization consists of spheres at the joint locations symbolizing the effort in terms of joint torques estimation. The colour scale ranges from green (i.e., minimum effort) to red (i.e., maximum effort), Fig. 3.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper is supported by EU An.Dy Project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 731540. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors. The European Commission or its services cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Fig. 2: Software architecture for real-time data acquisition and estimation.

Fig. 3: Real-time Rviz ROS visualization for the human gait application.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Miossec and A. Kheddar, "Human motion in cooperative tasks: Moving object case study," in *2008 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics*, pp. 1509–1514.
- [2] K. B. Reed and M. A. Peshkin, "Physical collaboration of human-human and human-robot teams," vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 108–120.
- [3] R. P. R. D. van der Wel, G. Knoblich, and N. Sebanz, "Let the force be with us: dyads exploit haptic coupling for coordination," vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 1420–1431.
- [4] Y. Tirupachuri, G. Nava, C. Latella, D. Ferigo, L. Rapetti, L. Tagliapietra, F. Nori, and D. Pucci, "Towards partner-aware humanoid robot control under physical interactions." [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1809.06165>
- [5] D. Roetenberg, H. Luinge, and P. Slycke, "Xsens MVN: Full 6dof human motion tracking using miniature inertial sensors." [Online]. Available: <http://human.kyst.com.tw/upload/downloadfs46130703234558070.pdf>
- [6] A. Wächter and L. T. Biegler, "On the implementation of an interior-point filter line-search algorithm for large-scale nonlinear programming," vol. 106, no. 1, pp. 25–57. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10107-004-0559-y>
- [7] C. Latella, S. Traversaro, D. Ferigo, Y. Tirupachuri, L. Rapetti, F. J. Andrade Chavez, F. Nori, and D. Pucci, "Simultaneous floating-base estimation of human kinematics and joint torques," vol. 19, no. 12, p. 2794. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/19/12/2794>
- [8] G. Metta, P. Fitzpatrick, and L. Natale, "YARP: Yet another robot platform," vol. 3, no. 1, p. 8. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5772/5761>
- [9] H. R. Kam, S.-H. Lee, T. Park, and C.-H. Kim, "RViz: a toolkit for real domain data visualization," vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 337–345. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11235-015-0034-5>